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Gender and Dance Motivation as determinants of Dance Style choice

Apple Joy Coronel¹, Renz Marion Tiglao¹, Realyn Solayao¹, Joseph Lobo^{1*}

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the relationship between gender and dance motivation to dance style choices of 85 students taking Bachelor of Performing Arts at City College of Angeles. The study was conducted through an online survey using Dance Motivation Questionnaire (DMQ). Frequency and percentage were used to describe the gender of the respondents, while Mean and Standard Deviation were used to describe the level of dance motivation, and ANOVA and Pearson's Chi-Square was used to determine the relationship between Dance Motivation and Gender to Dance Style Choices respectively. From the data obtained from the online survey questionnaire, it was found out there are 38 (n=44.71%) male and 47 (n=55.29%) female who answered the online survey. It was also found out that most of the respondents chose Hip-hop as their preferred dance style. The level of dance motivation of the respondents was found out to be moderately high. It was also found out that age and dance motivation have a significant relationship to students' dance style choice. Also, it was found out that there is a difference in dance style choice of the respondents based on gender. Overall, It was concluded that the gender and dance motivation are considered determinants of the dance style choice of students. Results obtained from this study provide new information to students, teachers, dance enthusiasts and researchers who are interested in conducting studies pertaining to gender, dance motivation and dance style choice. Further investigation is highly recommended to support the findings of this study.

INTRODUCTION

Dance is an art form solely based on bodily movement with the accompaniment through different forms and is a form of communication where performers may express themselves, send message, and let the viewers appreciate the art form itself. Human being expresses themselves naturally through movement. Dance transforms ordinary functional and expressive movement into an extraordinary movement for extraordinary drives; even a common movement such as walking is performed in dance in a decorated way, perhaps in circles or to a special rhythm, and it occurs in a special context. Dance may include a fixed vocabulary of movements that have no meaning in themselves, as in much of ballet and European folk dance, or drama and symbolic gestures may be used, as in many Asian dance forms. Peoples of different cultures dance otherwise and for varying purposes; their varied dance forms can reveal much about their way of life. There are different dance styles under the umbrella of this art form, and this study aims to understand the relationship between dance style choice according to individual differences such as gender and their motivation to dance.

Dance is a renowned human behavior seen in many cultures and is associated with ancient rites, gatherings, and social occasions (McCarty et al., 2017). It is a type of exercise that is tightly linked to music, creativity, and, in many cases, the presence and physical proximity of a partner (Maraz et al., 2015). Over the past few years, many students enjoy the different genres and styles of dance. There are seven dance styles which are the (Ballet, Contemporary, Jazz/Tap, Hip-Hop, Belly, Ballroom,

Latin) According to the Study of Barreiro & Furnham (2019), there are three Hundred and four Participants that indicate their styles and answered motivation questions for each one, and the Big Five personality qualities were all taken into consideration. For each dancing styles, factors analysis revealed three underlying motivation variables (mood enhancement, Fitness, and self-confidence). In six of the seven dance types, mood enhancement was the strongest predictor of dancing. It is understood that there are limitations.

In recent years, the literature has paid more attention to the reasons for dancing and the elements that influence one's decision to dance (Fink et al., 2021; McCarty et al., 2017). Some academics have looked into how personality factors, such as personality, influence dance preferences, and choices. In addition, there is an expanding amount of study concentrating on dancers' psychological, physiological, and mating motivations. This research aims to find out what motivates dancers in seven different styles. It is specifically looked at how these motives and individual variables such as demographics and personality traits influence the choice of a dance style.

Personality and Dance, Music choice (Chamorro-Premuzic et al., 2010), perception and experience of emotion in music (Eerola & Vuoskoski, 2013), and art preference are all linked to the Big Five personality traits. Studies have also shown a link between these five personality traits and recreational choice.

Dance is typically performed in mating situations and appears to serve as a human wooing display to attract potential partners. However, research in this area has primarily focused on how people perceive others'

¹ Program Coordinator, Physical Education Department, City College of Angeles, Angeles City, Pampanga, Philippines.

* Corresponding author's e-mail: josephlobo@cca.edu.ph

dancing rather than why they dance. Women derive quality cues (physical strength, personality) from men's dancing motions, and vice versa (fertility cues) have been discovered. Few empirical research has looked at why people choose to dance, but performance psychology seems to agree that the primary reason for participating in a performing art is to have fun. The majority of studies in this field, on the other hand, have adopted a descriptive-qualitative approach to assessment. For Folk, Ballet, Ballroom-competitive, and Modern dance, four elements were identified (namely, Self-expression, Social contact, Fitness, and Achievement/Performing) in order to discover underlying motivational factors of experienced dancers.

In this, the study aims to determine the relationship of dance style choice to gender and dance motivation of students taking up Bachelor of Performing Arts, which seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How may the respondents be described in terms of gender?
2. How may the dance style choices of respondents be described?
3. How may the level of motivation in dance of respondents be described?
4. Is there a significant relationship between gender and dance motivation to dance style choice of the respondents?

METHODOLOGY

The design of the study is descriptive-correlational which aims to determine the relationship of gender and dance motivation to the dance style choice of students pursuing Bachelor of Performing Arts (BPeA) at City College of Angeles, Philippines. Students from 1st year to 4th year are the target participants for the study. Universal sampling was utilized to gather samples. This sampling technique refers to selecting samples where not all the people in a population have the same probability of being part of the sample. The probability of being selected is unknown.

Two questionnaires were used in this study. The first part will gather respondents' gender and their preferred dance style (Ballet, Contemporary, Jazz/Tap, Hip-hop and Ballroom). The second part will be the adapted survey questionnaire from Lovatt (2017) which is the Dance Motivation Questionnaire (DMQ). This is a 24-item questionnaire that aims to measure and describe the level of motivation in dancing of the respondents. Responses are then recorded by a 4-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 4 (strongly agree).

Gathering of data from the target respondents was performed by sending a request letter first addressed to the Dean of the Institute of Education, Arts and Sciences. The questionnaires were floated via Google Form and all gathered data were exported to an Excel file and were used for analysis.

Frequency (f) and Percentage (%) were utilized to describe the gender and preferred dance style of the respondents.

On one hand, mean (M) and Standard Deviation (SD) were used to describe the level of dance motivation of the respondents. Lastly, ANOVA and Pearson's Chi-Square were used to determine the relationship of gender and dance motivation to dance style choice of BPeA Students. After the analyzation of data, the excel where all data are encoded was encrypted with a password where the researchers have only the sole access to it.

RESULTS

IBM SPSS 26 was used to perform the statistical treatment to the data gathered from the respondents.

Table 1 illustrates the gender of the respondents. There are 44.71% male which is equivalent to (n= 38) and 55.29% female which is (n= 47).

Table 2 presents the Dance Style Choices of BPeA Students. Based on the responses, it was found out that there are 48.24% of students answered Hip-Hop Dance, which is considered the highest chosen style (n= 41) followed by 32.94% of students who answered Contemporary, which is the second-highest (n= 28) and only 4.71% of the students answered Ballroom (n= 4) which is the lowest chosen dance style.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of Respondents

Gender	N	%
Male	38	44.71
Female	47	55.29

Table 2. Dance Style Choices

Gender	N	%
Ballet	5	5.88
Contemporary	28	32.94
Jazz/Tap	7	8.24
Hip-Hop	41	48.24
Ballroom	4	4.71

Table 3 describes the Dance Motivation of BPA Students. Based on the given results, most of the students responded that they participate in the dance because it is a good way to learn things that could be useful to them in their lives (M=3.36, SD=0.59) and because it is fun (M=3.35, SD=0.65) which both corresponds to a "Very High" interpretation. On the other hand, most of the respondents participate in dance because they enjoy it (M=3.34, SD=0.63), which corresponds to "Very High" and dance teaches self-discipline (M=3.20, SD=0.59) which corresponds to "Moderately High". Lastly, respondents participate in dance because they value its benefits (M=3.21, SD=0.61) which correspond to "Moderately High." Overall, the general weighted mean of Dance Motivation was found to be "Moderately High" (M= 3.02, SD= 0.42).

Table 4 illustrates the Correlation between Gender to Dance Style Choices. Pearson's chi-squared was run to determine the relationship between Gender to Dance Style Choices. This table found out that Male (n=21) and females (n=20) chose Hip-Hop as their Dance Style, which is the highest. The second most chosen Dance

style was Contemporary, Male (n=13) and Female (n=15) while the lowest chosen dance style was Ballroom, Male (n=0) and Female (n=4) with a p-value of (p=.266). It

was found that there is a significant correlation between Gender to Dance Style Choices.

Table 5 illustrates the Correlation between Gender to

Table 3. Level of Dance Motivation

Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation
I participate in dance because the benefits of dance are important to me	3.32	.061	Very High
I participate in dance because I find it pleasurable	3.29	.065	Very High
I participate in dance because I would feel ashamed if I quit	2.69	.085	Moderately High
I participate in dance because it is a good way to learn things which could be useful to me in my life	3.36	.059	Very High
I participate in dance because it allows me to live in a way that is true to my values.	3.24	.059	Moderately High
I participate in dance because it's an opportunity to just be who I am	3.26	.062	Moderately High
I participate in dance but I wonder what the point is	3.02	.068	Moderately High
I participate in dance but I question why I continue	2.88	0.71	Moderately High
I participate in dance because I value the benefits of dance	3.24	.061	Moderately High
I participate in dance because it's part of who I am	3.09	.700	Moderately High
I participate in dance because dancing is an expression of who I am	3.15	.715	Moderately High
I participate in dance because I would feel like a failure if I quit	2.71	.813	Moderately High
I participate in dance because it's fun	3.35	.064	Very High
I participate in dance because people push me to dance	2.92	.759	Moderately High
I participate in dance because I feel pressure from other people to dance	2.78	.792	Moderately High
I participate in dance because I feel obliged to continue	2.81	.731	Moderately High
I participate in dance but I question why I am putting myself through this	2.82	.804	Moderately High
I participate in dance because I would feel guilty if I quit	2.66	.866	Moderately High
I participate in dance because if I don't other people will not be pleased with me	2.61	.803	Moderately High
I participate in dance because I like it	3.24	.610	Moderately High
I participate in dance but the reasons why are not clear to me anymore	2.61	.817	Moderately High
I participate in dance because I enjoy it	3.34	.627	Moderately High
I participate in dance in order to satisfy people who want me to dance	2.94	.821	Moderately High
Overall	3.02	.439	Moderately High

Table 4. Association of Gender and Dance Style Choice

Dance Style Choice	Male	Female	X ²	df	p
Ballet	1	4	5.216	4	.266
Contemporary	13	15			
Jazz/Tap	3	4			
Hip-Hop	21	20			
Ballroom	0	4			

Dance Motivation. Eta correlation was run to determine the relationship between Gender to dance motivation, wherein Gender was identified as the Independent Variable, wherein Male has a mean of (M=3.12) and the female (M=2.95), which corresponds to “Moderately High” with an ANOVA value of (F=3.292) eta2 of (.038) with a p-value of (p=.073). The Dance Style Choice, wherein most students chose Hip-Hop with the highest mean (M=3.10) and were found to be “Moderately High”. These dance styles have an ANOVA value of (F=.801) eta2 of (.039) with a p-value of (p=.528). Overall results show that there is a significant correlation between Gender to Dance Motivation.

DISCUSSION

In the demographic of Bachelor of Performing Arts (BPeA) students in terms of gender, most of the respondents who answered the Dance Motivation

Table 5. Association of Dance Motivation and Dance Style Choice

Dance Style Choice					
Ballet	3.08	.801	.196	.039	.528
Contemporary	2.97				
Jazz/Tap	2.90				
Hip-Hop	3.10				
Ballroom	2.79				

Questionnaire (DMQ) are mostly female than male from the total sample for the study. Also, the dance style choice that was favored by most of the respondents is Hip-hop, followed by Contemporary, Jazz/Tap, Ballet and Ballroom respectively. It can be construed that most of the students who answered the survey highly favored Hip-hop because of the rapid growth and popularity of Hip-hop culture in the Philippines.

In regards to the dance motivation of the students, most of the respondents participates in dance because they perceived that they enjoy doing it, the fun (Bond & Stinson, 2007) that it can give while performing and a good way to learn things which can be useful to their individual lives. Furthermore, students participate in dancing because it teaches them how to be disciplined, well-organize, and the value behind the art form physically and mentally. Overall, results can be interpreted that the dance motivation level of the students is moderately high.

In the analysis of the relationship between Gender to Dance motivation; the finding revealed that, there is a positive significant relationship between the two based on the Pearson's chi-square test that was performed. Furthermore, it was also found out that there is a difference between gender based on their preferred dance style. It was found out that most of the male respondents chose Hip-hop compare to female. Also, female respondents chose Contemporary compare to male. In terms of Jazz/Tap and Ballet, most of the female respondents chose the said dance style compare to male. Lastly, ballroom dance was most favored by the female respondents compare to males because no respondents chose this specific dance style. Previous studies stated that dance styles have distinct expectations about the role of men and women must conquer or live up to. Gender stereotyping have always existed, but more people tried to break down those boundaries and challenge today's norm which is highly brave move, especially in the field of art. Overall analysis revealed that, there is a significant relationship between the two.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the researchers concluded that among the dance style choice that were mentioned to this study, Hip-hop is the most preferred dance style choice of the Bachelor of Performing Arts students. It was also found out that the level of dance motivation of the students is moderately high.

Lastly, the relationship of gender and dance motivation to dance style choice; the results yielded a significant relationship between the variables and researchers concluded that there is difference between male and female regarding their preferred dance style. Most of the male respondents preferred Hip-hop than female; Contemporary, Jazz/Tap, Ballet and Ballroom dance are highly preferred by female compare to male. Regarding the correlation between Dance Motivation and Dance Style choice, the researchers concluded that the level of motivation of students is related to their preferred dance style.

The main goal of this study is to determine the relationship of gender and dance motivation to dance style choice of the students. Overall, the researchers concluded that gender and dance motivation are determinants of the preferred dance style of students. However, these findings are not yet conclusive and further investigation is highly recommended.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, the researchers recommended the following:

1. Regarding to dance motivation of the students, the researchers highly recommend that experts like professional dancers, choreographers, and teachers who are under the Physical and Performing Arts Department

should motivate the students to engage themselves in dancing and provide programs where they engage themselves (e.g., webinar, seminar, dance showcase and history of dance) wherein they will train their students and give them enough knowledge about different dance styles and how it may affect them physically, socially and mentally. In this way, students will explore more about dance, and they can enhance their skills through exposing themselves in dancing. This can be a way for them to realize what dance styles they prefer and enjoy.

2. Since the result of this study is not yet conclusive, it is highly recommended that further investigation can be conducted particularly in the components that were measured in this study. Additional respondents and variables can also be added to this existing research and utilize other statistical methods that may support or contradict the findings of this study.

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